

Integrating Predictive Power Market Modelling with Automated Demand-Side Management of Residential Heat Pumps

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Abstract — The recent introduction of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in the electrical grid has led to significant challenges in balancing electricity supply and demand, especially in volatile power markets. This paper explores a preliminary design of a cloud-orchestrated Energy Management System (EMS) that integrates predictive power market modelling with automated demand-side management of residential Heat Pumps (HPs). By leveraging Machine Learning (ML)-based forecasting and Internet of Things (IoT)-enabled control mechanisms, the system envisions to dynamically optimise HP operations in response to electricity price fluctuations. Preliminary results of the proposed system within the META BUILD project are presented, focusing on modelling and forecasting the Greek day ahead market power prices. Identified challenges and future work are also discussed.

Keywords — Predictive modelling, demand-side management, energy optimisation, heat pumps, cloud orchestration, machine learning, electricity markets.

I. INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

The European transition towards renewable energy sources has transformed modern electricity grids, driven by efforts to reduce carbon emissions [1] [2]. However, the intermittent and variable nature of these resources presents challenges for maintaining grid stability and aligning supply with demand. Geopolitical tensions and unforeseen disruptions have recently created challenges across both wholesale and retail sectors. Power markets have been characterised by high volatility and uncertainty, compelling energy stakeholders to develop innovative management strategies and adaptive approaches to mitigate risks [3][4].

Contemporary European energy systems are navigating an increasingly complex landscape, characterised by challenges that emerge from the interplay of volatile power markets, the inherent variability of renewable energy sources and the rapidly escalating residential electricity demand [5]. Residential Heat Pumps, while representing a promising

technology for sustainable heating and cooling, currently operate as relatively autonomous devices that frequently function in isolation from broader market dynamics and grid intelligence. Without dynamic end-to-end intelligent monitoring and control mechanisms, users and utilities miss opportunities to optimise energy consumption and management, aligning their operations with market price signals or local renewable energy availability.

Demand-Side Management (DSM) offers a pathway to actively involve consumers in energy optimisation, while predictive modelling of power markets provides actionable insights into electricity prices and demand trends. Integrating these capabilities within a cloud-based framework enables the real-time monitoring and control of residential energy devices, particularly HPs, which represent an emergent component of residential heating and cooling systems [6].

This paper investigates the integration of predictive market modelling and DSM, within a cloud-based system, with a focus on dynamically managing HP operation with an aim of optimising energy use and cost. This preliminary effort is part of the ongoing EU funded project META BUILD [7].

This technological disconnection creates multifaceted inefficiencies that can reverberate across both individual consumer experiences and broader utility ecosystems. Despite the existence of power market forecasting algorithms [8] and automated residential DSM approaches [9], an orchestrated energy management solution which optimises the two strands in tandem with each other, offering a scalable solution in a cloud environment is still in a nascent phase [10] [11].

This gap serves as the foundation of an initial conceptual framework that is being developed within META BUILD to advance analytics in a cloud environment might transform the interaction between residential energy-intensive devices, such as HPs and complex wholesale market dynamics, such as price forecasting and management operations.

The proposed architecture is work-in-progress and thus deliberately exploratory. It is characterised by high-level conceptualisation of different modules and early-stage results

and challenges of preliminary predictive modelling experiments of the Greek power market, where the indented use case is scheduled to be implemented in the future. These early-stage investigations aim to lay the groundwork for more developments, acknowledging the complexity of bridging advanced predictive analytics with practical energy management solutions.

II. PROPOSED CLOUD-BASED EMS

The proposed cloud-orchestrated EMS is based on a business use case combining predictive modelling of power markets with automated DSM for residential HPs (Heat Pumps). This approach dynamically aligns energy consumption, market operations and pricing strategies to maximise economic efficiency for both utilities and end users. Below, we briefly discuss the high-level components of dynamic and orchestrated scheduling, Time-of-Use (ToU) optimisation and automated HP load management.

A. Dynamic Scheduling of Market Operations

One of the primary business drivers of the proposed solution is its ability to forecast wholesale power market prices (e.g., day-ahead and intra-day markets) and orchestrate dynamic energy operations [12]. This capability enables better trading strategies that can potentially enhance market participation efficiency. Under the identified scenario, the participating utility purchases power during forecasted low-price hours, such as mid-day periods and sells it during forecasted high-price periods, typically during evening peaks. This strategic approach allows utilities to optimise their market positioning and their timing of energy transactions.

The integration of Time-of-Use (ToU) rates and dynamic pricing represents another aspect of market operations scheduling. The participating utility can monitor market conditions and adjust electricity rates based on predicted market prices. A typical implementation involves offering lower rates during periods of excess renewable generation at the system level, which can create financial incentives for Heat Pump operation during these advantageous timeframes. This approach can yield benefits for residential consumers, who can permit automated responses to these price signals, while also considering potential local power generation from roof-top photovoltaics. The end result might be a reduction in electricity costs without compromising comfort levels, creating a win-win scenario for both utilities and consumers.

By intelligently coordinating these market operations, the system can create a responsive ecosystem that can adapt to changing market conditions, while optimising energy utilisation and cost efficiency across the entire value chain. This dynamic scheduling capability forms the foundation for a more integrated and responsive energy marketplace that benefits all stakeholders.

B. Heat Pump Automated Load Management

HPs, as potentially flexible thermal devices, are suited to dynamic load management and direct load control [13]. By leveraging predictive market insights and IoT-based cloud orchestration, the system can optimise HP operation through several sophisticated approaches.

Pre-heating and pre-cooling strategies during low-price periods form an important aspect of this optimisation process. The predictive model identifies mid-day periods when Day-Ahead Market (DAM) prices are forecasted to be low, often

due to increased renewable energy generation, particularly from solar sources. During these favorable price windows, the heat pump pre-heats or pre-cools the participating residential homes, effectively utilising inexpensive electricity to store thermal energy within the building's structure.

Complementing this approach is the minimisation of Heat Pump operation during high-price periods. During forecasted high-price intervals, typically occurring during evening peak hours from 17:00 to 21:00, Heat Pump operation can be deliberately reduced without compromising the comfort parameters established for the residents. This reduction can be made possible by the home's thermal inertia, which maintains comfortable indoor temperatures even with reduced heating or cooling system activity during these high-cost periods.

Through this intelligent orchestration of thermal energy management, the system tends to create a balance between energy cost optimisation and residential comfort. The automated nature of these control strategies enable seamless integration with market dynamics, requiring no active intervention from residents, while still preserving their comfort preferences and potentially generating meaningful cost savings.

C. Value Proposition

The proposed integrated system can deliver benefits across multiple stakeholder groups, creating a comprehensive value proposition that addresses both individual and systemic needs in the energy ecosystem.

For residential consumers, the system can offer financial advantages through cost savings achieved by automated Heat Pump scheduling. By aligning heat pump operations with low-price periods, the system can reduce electricity bills without compromising the thermal comfort parameters essential for resident satisfaction. Beyond financial benefits, the suggested solution provides convenience through IoT-enabled cloud orchestration that ensures optimal scheduling without requiring manual intervention. This automation can maintain user comfort, while eliminating the need for residents to actively monitor or adjust their systems in response to market fluctuations.

Utilities and aggregators can be benefitted by market optimisation capabilities through the platform. Participating utilities can aggregate residential loads strategically and participate in relevant energy markets with greater effectiveness, maximising trading opportunities by leveraging the collective flexibility of multiple residential Heat Pumps. This aggregation can also create new revenue generation pathways through dynamic pricing mechanisms that incentivise consumer behaviour change. These pricing structures might enable utilities to recover operational costs, while potentially improving their overall profitability through more efficient market participation.

The benefits might extend beyond individual stakeholders to include grid operators and policy-makers. By dynamically shifting demand away from peak periods through coordinated Heat Pump management, the system helps minimise stress on the electrical grid. This load-shifting capability supports the gradual increase in sustainable reliance on renewable energy sources, as demand can be more effectively aligned with periods of abundant renewable generation. The resulting grid stability improvements contribute to broader energy transition

goals while reducing the need for costly infrastructure upgrades.

Through this multi-faceted value proposition, the system creates a virtuous cycle where individual consumer benefits align with utility objectives and broader system-level improvements, fostering a more efficient, sustainable and responsive energy ecosystem.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The preliminary system architecture integrates predictive modelling, IoT-enabled HP management and cloud-based DSM to dynamically optimise energy operations. The initial design incorporates three core modules: (a) a DAM forecasting module using data-driven ML techniques, (b) HP monitoring and control operations and (c) cloud orchestration of DSM, enabling collaborative optimisation between tenants and utilities. The high-level system architecture is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. High-Level System Architecture

A. Day-Ahead Market (DAM) Forecasting Module

The DAM forecasting module predicts electricity prices for the next day using a combination of renewable generation forecasts and system load projections, as well as other power market data. The DAM forecasting module ingests the above data types from multiple sources via Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), creating a unified pipeline. This module leverages advanced ML techniques to analyse time-series data and detect patterns in market behaviour.

The module's input architecture encompasses diverse data sources that provide a comprehensive view of market conditions. From the Transmission System Operator (TSO), the system obtains critical renewable energy data including solar, wind and hydro generation forecasts via dedicated APIs. System load projections broken down by hourly intervals are also acquired through TSO interfaces. Complementing this operational data, the module ingests extensive Energy Market Operator logs, which include historical DAM prices delivered through APIs that provide hourly market clearing prices from previous sessions. The system also incorporates anonymised bidding behaviour information, enabling deeper insights into price-setting mechanisms, along with hourly export and import data at the grid-wide level.

The cloud-based forecasting process involves sophisticated data handling and analysis techniques. Initially, inputs undergo pre-processing to normalise data formats (e.g.,

converting half-hour measurements to hourly values) and detect anomalies like missing values. The ingested data is then streamed into a cloud-enabled processing pipeline platform, (i.e., Apache Airflow), ensuring real-time data availability throughout the system. API mechanisms facilitate seamless data exchange between the storage layer (implemented using technologies like PostgreSQL) and the forecasting models hosted on frameworks such as Anaconda. For the predictive modelling itself, advanced machine learning algorithms like XGBoost [14] are employed to predict hourly DAM prices. XGBoost libraries demonstrate particular effectiveness in capturing the temporal dependencies and patterns characteristic of energy markets.

The module produces output in several valuable formats designed for operational use. Hourly DAM price forecasts serve as the primary output, informing Heat Pump operations scheduling and guiding energy market participation strategies. These forecasts are exposed through a REST API for consumption by both the DSM platform and Heat Pump controllers, enabling coordinated decision-making across the system. Additionally, the module generates forecast confidence metrics, such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), which indicate model reliability and enable ongoing monitoring and proactive adjustments to the forecasting approach.

B. Heat Pump Operations Module

This module monitors and models the fundamental operations of IoT-enabled heat pumps to facilitate dynamic control based on market signals and user preferences. The HPs (Heat Pumps) are equipped with cloud-enabled IoT controllers that provide real-time monitoring capabilities and establish bidirectional communication channels with the cloud platform, creating a responsive and intelligent thermal management system.

The Heat Pump Monitoring API forms the core of the module's data collection capabilities. Heat pumps transmit operational data including energy consumption metrics, flow temperature readings and indoor/outdoor temperature measurements through this interface. The cloud platform aggregates and stores this data via dedicated APIs, enabling comprehensive historical analysis and providing the necessary information base for implementing dynamic control strategies. This monitoring ensures that the system maintains awareness of current conditions, while building a historical performance profile for each connected device.

Control functionality is implemented through a set of specialised APIs designed for heat pump management. The cloud platform can send precise on/off commands to activate or deactivate heat pumps during specific time windows, particularly targeting low-price periods for operation. Setpoint adjustment capabilities allow for dynamic modification of the heat pump's target temperature parameters, enabling alignment with price signals and user preferences. This functionality supports advanced strategies such as pre-heating or pre-cooling residential spaces during favourable price conditions. Further enhancing control precision, the system can adjust water flow temperature—the temperature of water supplied to the heating system—via dedicated API endpoints, optimising energy efficiency while maintaining comfort parameters.

The monitoring framework captures several operational parameters to ensure optimal performance. Energy

consumption tracking provides visibility into the electricity utilised by each heat pump, enabling cost calculations and efficiency assessments. Indoor temperature monitoring ensures that tenant comfort is maintained by keeping ambient conditions within acceptable ranges, typically between 20–22°C. Runtime metrics tracking provides insights into operational efficiency, including compressor activity patterns and cycling behaviours where device capabilities permit such monitoring.

C. Cloud-Orchestrated DSM Module

The DSM module functions as the central coordination hub for the entire system, orchestrating the interplay between market forecasts, tenant preferences and HP operations through a network of APIs that enable communication between components. This central position allows the module to synthesise information from multiple sources and implement optimised operational strategies that balance economic, comfort and efficiency considerations.

The Market Forecast Integration API serves as the primary channel for incorporating price intelligence into operational decisions. Through this interface, the DSM module retrieves comprehensive hourly DAM price forecasts via REST APIs exposed by the forecasting module. This flow of pricing data provides the foundation for economically optimised scheduling decisions, allowing the system to target low-cost periods for energy-intensive operations while minimising activity during high-price intervals.

Complementing this market intelligence, the Heat Pump Data Aggregation API establishes a bidirectional information flow between devices and the central platform. Individual heat pumps transmit detailed telemetry data through these APIs to the DSM platform, creating a comprehensive operational awareness. The platform leverages this granular device-level data to create a virtualised, aggregated load profile that participating utilities can utilise for market bidding activities. This aggregation capability transforms distributed residential thermal assets into a cohesive resource that can be managed in response to market conditions.

The system produces actionable outputs through dedicated Optimisation Outputs APIs that translate analytical insights into concrete operational schedules. Advanced optimisation algorithms within the DSM module generate detailed operational instructions that are transmitted to each heat pump via the respective API interfaces. A representative schedule might direct a heat pump to operate during the 12:00–15:00 timeframe when DAM prices are forecasted to be low, while remaining idle during the 18:00–21:00 period when prices typically peak. The system also maintains continuous monitoring of runtime metrics to validate operational efficiency and ensure that performance matches expectations, enabling ongoing refinement of control strategies.

The cloud-based DSM design should incorporate several architectural considerations to ensure system reliability and effectiveness. Scalability must allow the cloud infrastructure to accommodate the addition of new data pipelines, connected devices and forecasting computations with minimal impact on performance and operational costs. Data security measures should include token-based authentication and potential encryption technologies to ensure secure communication between the DSM platform, forecasting module and connected heat pumps. Latency management should be prioritised through lightweight API implementations that

minimise communication delays, ensuring control commands reach HPs promptly and maintain system responsiveness under dynamic operating conditions.

IV. EARLY-STAGE RESULTS

1) Data Collection

The dataset for early-stage experiments was sourced from two energy market and system operator platforms, covering a broad spectrum of power system and market data. The initially collected data spans from September 2024 to January 2025, focusing on the Greek electricity market, which serves as the primary testbed for this META-BUILD use case.

- Greek TSO (IPTO) [16]: Includes transmission system operator forecasted data such as total system load, renewable energy generation (e.g., solar, wind, hydro), and net load balance.
- Greek Energy Market (EnExGroup) [17]: Comprises buy/sell order logs, import/export transactions and clearing prices from the day-ahead market.

2) Data Preprocessing

To ensure data quality and enhance model performance, the following preprocessing steps were applied:

- Date-time transformation: Conversion of timestamps into structured datetime objects with extracted temporal features such as hour, day of the week and month.
- Handling Missing Values: Implemented forward-filling and interpolation techniques to manage data gaps.
- Feature Scaling: Robust Scaler was applied to normalise the numerical features, ensuring extreme values do not disproportionately impact model training.

3) Feature Engineering

To capture temporal dependencies and enhance predictive capability, key derived features include:

- Lag Features: Created 24-hour and 48-hour lagged DAM prices to incorporate recent price trends.
- Rolling Statistics: Computed 24-hour moving averages and rolling standard deviations to capture short-term fluctuations.
- Log Transformation: Applied logarithmic scaling to stabilise DAM price variance and reduce heteroscedasticity.

4) Model Training

A series of predictive models were analysed, with an emphasis on ML-based forecasting.

- Data Splitting: The dataset is divided into training set (0.8) and validation set (0.2).
- Hyperparameter Optimisation: Applied *RandomizedSearchCV* to fine-tune key parameters (e.g., learning rate, max depth, and regularisation) for gradient-boosted models.
- Time-Series Cross-Validation: Time Series Split was used to ensure that the validation set follows the training period preventing data leakage.

- **Model-Fitting:** The most promising model was trained on the scaled training data.

5) Model Evaluation

Performance was assessed on a DAM prediction for 23/01/2025, as a preliminary and sample result, using industry-standard error metrics [15] as shown in Table I, with the validation set depicted in Fig. 2 and the prediction results presented in Fig. 3.

TABLE I. EVALUATION RESULTS

<i>Metric</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>MAPE</i>	<i>R²</i>
23/01/2025 DAM Prediction	5.09	0.039	0.97

Fig. 2. Validation set

Fig. 3. Prediction result and evaluation

V. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The proposed cloud-orchestrated Energy Management System brings forward an integration of predictive market modelling with residential HP management. This approach encompasses several challenges that require thoughtful consideration and strategic planning. Market forecasting accuracy presents a fundamental challenge, particularly during periods of heightened volatility, when the reliability of day-ahead market price predictions may deteriorate. To address this concern, our ongoing work focuses on incorporating additional input variables and designing more robust pipeline injection mechanisms that can enhance model stability even under turbulent market conditions. This refinement process includes expanding data sources beyond the current framework, developing continuous model retraining protocols and designing well-structured APIs that can seamlessly deliver forecast outputs to the orchestration and demand-side management modules.

The integration landscape presents its own complexities, particularly regarding device compatibility across diverse HP manufacturers with proprietary protocols and varying connectivity capabilities. Future integration work will extend into the monitoring and modelling domain, where we are collecting detailed telemetry data encompassing energy usage patterns, runtime metrics, setpoint temperatures and flow temperature dynamics. These datasets will inform the development of behavioural models that can characterise HP operations under various conditions and optimise control strategies accordingly. As this work progresses, we will carefully assess the impact of load shifting on both energy efficiency and tenant satisfaction, ensuring that optimisation efforts balance economic benefits with comfort preservation.

Energy market regulations introduce another layer of complexity, as these frameworks vary substantially across countries. The inherent differences in market structures necessitate a modular, highly configurable system design that can adapt to diverse environments, without requiring fundamental architectural changes. This adaptability extends to our orchestration module, which we are designing as a flexible, pipeline-based framework with robust automation capabilities and sophisticated decision-making algorithms. The module design will emphasise on interoperability and extensibility, allowing for seamless integration of new components and adaptation to evolving market conditions.

User engagement represents an important social dimension, as tenants may initially view dynamic load management as potentially intrusive or disruptive to their comfort preferences. Our approach emphasises transparent communication about system benefits and operational characteristics. This user-centric perspective connects closely with data privacy considerations, as the collection and transmission of energy consumption data and temperature preferences must adhere to stringent protection standards, particularly those outlined in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Scalability considerations may become increasingly important as the system expands to incorporate more connected HPs and additional data sources. A growing volume of telemetry information, control commands and market intelligence will demand robust infrastructure and highly efficient approaches.

The on-going work toward a fully realised cloud-orchestrated Energy Management System requires continued advancement across these interconnected domains. By systematically addressing challenges while pursuing refinements in forecasting capabilities, HP control mechanisms and orchestration methodologies, we aim to create a cohesive system that balances economic efficiency, user comfort, and technical robustness. The preliminary results from our day-ahead market forecasting experiments provide encouraging evidence that this approach can deliver actionable intelligence for optimising energy operations, while our ongoing work streams focus on translating this potential into practical benefits for utilities, consumers and the broader energy ecosystem.

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